

Healthy mothers with normal cardiotocograms at term. Is maternal age a true determinant of perinatal outcome?

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ABSTRACT

Objective: to study the true determinants of adverse perinatal outcome (APO) in term healthy mothers with normal cardiotocograms (CTG), evaluating the real influence of maternal age.

Material and methods: In a retrospective study, we assessed a group of 529 term healthy mothers with normal CTGs that regardless of maternal age, evolved spontaneously up to 41 ± 2 weeks. The result of the conservative management was evaluated by means of univariable and multivariable logistic regression analysis, determining the association of maternal age and other clinical and ultrasonographical parameters with APO.

Result: In contrast with low CPR MoM (OR=0.155, P=0.014), induction of labor (OR=2.273, P=0.023) and low parity (OR=0.494, P=0.026), maternal age and birth weight centile did not prove to be true determinants of perinatal outcome. The multivariable model for prediction of APO using clinical parameters presented a sensitivity of 35% and 27% for a false positive rate of 10% and 5%, AUC 0.736 (95% CI 0.655-0.818), P<0.0001).

Conclusions: in healthy old mothers with normal CTGs at term, APO is determined by low CPR, existence of labor induction and low parity, while no real influence was observed for maternal age, fetal smallness, and interval examination-delivery. These results do not support the current consensus on induction at earlier weeks to prevent adverse outcome in all cases of advanced maternal age, advocating for a more individualized, customized, and less interventional management based on fetal hemodynamics.

Key Words:

Doppler ultrasound, late-onset fetal growth restriction, fetal smallness, labor induction.

INTRODUCTION

In the absence of vascular disease caused by chronic hypertension, early-onset preeclampsia, thrombophilia and type I diabetes, most fetal growth disorders follow the late-onset pattern¹, developing after 32-34 weeks, running undercurrent without making striking symptomatic manifestations, and remaining unnoticed until term, when induction for fetal smallness is usually indicated in the belief that it avoids adverse perinatal outcome (APO)². In other situations, despite fetal growth is under normal range, induction is scheduled for advanced maternal age^{3,4}, considering this parameter can cause APO by itself, regardless of the accompanying maternal and fetal characteristics.

Therefore, from a practical point of view, a frequent scenario at term is that in which fetuses whose mother is over 40 years old become induced at 39-40 weeks, despite the existence of a good maternal health, a previous uneventful gestation, and a reactive term cardiotocogram CTG. The rationale of this management lies in studies that associate maternal age with APO²⁻⁴. However, most of them were not performed using a multivariable perspective and did not adjust for important potential confounders like fetal hemodynamics, whose best representative at term is cerebroplacental ratio (CPR)⁵. Prompted by this controversy, we aimed to clarify the real influence of the different clinical and ultrasonographical parameters, especially maternal age, on perinatal outcome at term, studying their interaction in term pregnancies with good maternal health and normal CTG.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This was a retrospective study of 529 fetuses attending at the public tertiary maternity of La Fe hospital (Institution Review Board and Hospital Ethics Committee permission number 2016/0453). All fetuses underwent a CTG and a Doppler ultrasound examination at term, which included fetal biometry and interrogation of the umbilical (UA) and middle cerebral artery (MCA) pulsatility indices (PI). UA PI and MCA PI were recorded using color and pulse Doppler according to earlier descriptions⁶⁻⁷, while CPR was calculated as the simple ratio between MCA PI and UA PI⁸. In order to adjust for the effect of the GA, birth weight (BW) values were converted into local reference centiles⁹ adjusting also for fetal gender, and CPR values were converted into multiples of median (MoM) dividing each value by the 50th centile at each gestational age as earlier described⁶. CPR medians (50th centile) were represented by the following equation:

$$\text{CPR 50}^{\text{th}} \text{ centile} = -3.814786276 + 0.36363249 * \text{GA} - 0.005646672 * \text{GA}^2.$$

Where GA was gestational age in weeks with decimals.

All Doppler examinations were performed by the first author, a certified teaching expert in obstetric ultrasound by the Spanish Society of Obstetrics and Gynecology, using General Electric Voluson® (E8/E6/730) ultrasound machines (General Electric Healthcare, Spain) with 2-8 MHz convex probes, during fetal quiescence, in the absence of fetal tachycardia, and keeping the insonation angle with the examined vessels as small as possible and always below 30°. GA was determined according to the crown-rump length in the first trimester. Multiple pregnancies and those complicated by congenital fetal abnormalities were excluded. Only one examination (the last) was included in the study.

According to our hospital protocol, appropriate-for-gestational-age (AGA) fetuses are left to evolve spontaneously until 41±2 weeks, while small-for-gestational-age (SGA) fetuses (BW<10th centile) and growth restricted fetuses (BW <3rd centile or SGA plus an abnormal CPR) are respectively induced at 40 weeks and 38-40 weeks, depending on the FGR

severity. In addition to this protocol, fetuses born to mothers older than 40 years tend to be induced at 40 weeks to avoid possible adverse outcome and minimize risks.

However, in this particular study group, all fetuses were exceptionally left to evolve spontaneously until the end of gestation. Therefore, regardless of maternal age and fetal weight, all pregnancies with good maternal health and normal CTG were induced only for prolonged pregnancy and not earlier than 41 ± 2 days. Induction was performed according to the hospital protocol: In fetuses with favorable Bishop score, oxytocin was the treatment of choice. In the remaining fetuses, vaginal prostaglandins (Propess®) or a cervical balloon were placed the first day, followed, in the absence of labor contractions, by oxytocin induction the next day.

The main reason behind this conservative management was the maternal will to continue pregnancy without obstetrical intervention in fetuses with borderline smallness, provided the existence of a normal CTG and a good maternal health. Due to the inaccuracy of fetal biometry, many cases with borderline smallness turned out to be smaller than expected at birth. These cases were good models to evaluate the associations between maternal age, fetal weight and APO as despite being small or born to older mothers were conducted spontaneously until induction at 41 ± 2 weeks.

In this regard, APO was considered when the composite adverse outcome was positive for any of these 4 components: abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate or intrapartum fetal scalp pH <7.20 requiring cesarean section, neonatal umbilical artery cord pH <7.20 , 5 minute Apgar score <7 , and postpartum admission to the neonatal intensive care unit or special care baby unit. Abnormal intrapartum fetal heart rate was classified according to the intrapartum fetal monitoring guidelines of the FIGO¹⁰. According to this classification, an abnormal CTGs was considered in case of baseline heart rate below 100 bpm, reduced variability, sinusoidal pattern and repetitive late or prolonged decelerations. In addition, in case of suspicious CTG, (for example, repetitive or atypical variable decelerations), a fetal

scalp blood sample was performed to evaluate fetal pH and cesarean section was indicated if this was below 7.20. The reasons for NICU admission were mainly respiratory distress and perinatal depression (signs of labored breathing that required respiratory support or even resuscitation), followed by hypoglycemia and jaundice. In this regard, as all neonates were delivered at term, the need for resuscitation was assumed to reflect different degrees of perinatal hypoxia and related with adverse outcome.

To rule out the possibility of selection and intervention bias, all cases were selected at the first examination, started labor spontaneously and were induced only at 41 weeks without any earlier intervention. Pregnancies with medical disorders, like diabetes type-I and hypertensive disease, or pathological CTGs were considered for induction as per hospital protocol and discarded from the study.

Gestational characteristics including maternal age, weight, height, body mass index (BMI), parity, number of gestations and ethnicity were taken at examination and therefore were obtained from the hospital files together with ultrasound parameters. After delivery, labor data including BW, BW centile, mode of delivery, 5 minutes Apgar score, cord arterial pH and baby destiny were also collected.

Association between clinical parameters and APO was evaluated by means of univariable and multivariable analysis, including as dependent variables several maternal and fetal parameters, like maternal age, body mass index, parity, smoking, CPR MoM, interval examination-labor, existence of labor induction, fetal sex, and BW centile. Accuracy of the multivariable model for the prediction of APO was calculated by means of ROC analysis.

Continuous and categorical variables were compared using Mann-Whitney U and Fisher tests. P-values below 0.05 were considered significant. Graphs were constructed with GraphPad Prism[®] 5.0a and statistical analysis were done with StatPlus Mac:Pro[®] 7.3.3.0, both for Apple Macintosh[®].

RESULTS

The characteristics of the study population are shown in table 1. It included 528 mothers and fetuses evaluated at term (37+0 - 41+6 weeks), of which 274 (51.9%) were males. The mean maternal age, parity and BMI were 32.2, 0.65 and 23.6, and the mean GA at examination and delivery 39.2 and 40.4 weeks with a mean interval examination-labor of 8 days. Most pregnancies initiated labor spontaneously (70.1%) and delivered spontaneously (64%) and most neonates were born uneventfully, accompanying the mother to the maternity ward (97.9%). Moreover, despite 12% of fetuses were below the 10th centile, only 2 (0.4%) presented Apgar score below 7 at 5 minutes and 8 (1.5%) a cord pH below 7.10.

Table 2 and figure 1 compare the characteristics of the groups with normal outcome and APO. Mothers in the APO group had a lower parity ($P<0.05$), delivered later ($P<0.01$) and had a higher frequency of labor induction ($P<0.01$). In addition their fetuses presented lower CPR MoM ($P<0.01$). Contrarily, no differences were observed concerning maternal age, BW centile, body mass index, interval to labor, frequency of SGA, smoking and fetal gender.

Finally, table 3 and figure 2 show the multivariable linear regression analysis for the explanation of APO. Only CPR MoM (OR 0.155, $P<0.05$), induction of labor (OR 2.273, $P<0.05$) and parity (OR 0.494, $P<0.05$) were selected as significant parameter, while no influence was observed for BW and maternal age. The model showed a moderate accuracy (sensitivity of 35% and 27% for a false positive rate of 10% and 5%, AUC=0.736, 95% CI= 0.655-0.818, $P<0.0001$).

DISCUSSION

Principal findings

According to our results and provided the existence of a good maternal health and a normal CTG pattern (the most frequent scenario) perinatal outcome at term does not depend on fetal weight, maternal age, body mass index and interval examination-delivery but on CPR, parity and induction of labor.

Clinical implications

Due to the physiopathology of late-onset growth disorders, pregnancies with normal 32-34 weeks ultrasound may present at term with unexpected low estimated fetal weight, representing an important concern for the managing obstetrician who, according to current management guides^{1,2} may perform early induction for fetal weight. In addition, many other mothers may be also induced prior to the expected delivery date regardless of fetal growth and wellbeing simply for the existence of maternal age >40. In this regard, our results have shown several relevant aspects: First, that fetal weight by itself is not a true determinant of APO. Accordingly, the higher incidence of APO earlier described in small fetuses^{11,12} might be in fact related with abnormal fetal hemodynamics and not with fetal weight. Second, that neither maternal age, nor BMI have a role in determining outcome. Interestingly, this proves that age by itself does not confer a risk in women whose health is not affected by diseases influencing pregnancy. In fact, despite older women and women with high BMI are likely to hypertension, diabetes and many other diseases¹³⁻¹⁹, healthy old women unaffected by these disorders may present similar possibilities of APO than youngsters as suggested previously²⁰. Concerning the interval examination-delivery, the optimal regimen has not been established, varying between one and two controls per week²¹. Our data suggest that the number of days between examination and labor (reflecting the number of days without control) does not influence perinatal outcome, probably because the

magnitude of the variation in fetal hemodynamics is insufficient to modify outcome. In this regard, exhaustive fetal controls are more a soothing balm for patients and obstetricians than an evidence-based medical practice.

Regarding the factors that do influence APO, we found an effect for CPR, parity and induction of labor. CPR influence has been earlier described, being much more reliable than estimation of fetal weight for the prediction of APO²². Concerning parity, despite previous works suggested a relationship between multiparity and adverse outcome, our data indicated the opposite relationship, being the influence on APO more intense in nulliparous women. The reason for the former association might be related with the higher prevalence of older age, obesity and maternal disease affecting pregnancy in multiparous women^{23,24}. Conversely, the observed increment of APO in primiparous women^{25,26} or in women undergoing induction might be a mechanical phenomenon related with the effort needed to overcome the resistance to cervical effacement, as recently suggested²⁷.

Proposal of management in fetuses at term with normal CTG and good maternal health

Different protocols for the management of the fetus at term have been proposed. On one hand and based on a ponderal perspective, some authors screen for adverse outcome using fetal weigh. Accordingly, AGA fetuses are followed with a less interventional management until 41 weeks, while SGA fetuses are induced prior to expected (38-40 weeks) depending on the magnitude of smallness and association with abnormal Doppler (growth restriction). On the other hand, other authors have proposed a universal induction at 39 weeks, suggesting an improvement in the prognosis of the induced population²⁸⁻³³.

Considering our data, a better strategy might be to screen for APO using a hemodynamic customized approach by means of CPR in order to select fetuses with enough functional reserve to follow a less interventional management. Unfortunately, the influence of the ponderal perspective has so far avoided such a change, despite the continuous evidence

in favor of the hemodynamic proposal^{22,34}.

Strengths and limitations

The main strengths of this work are the study at unison of clinical and sonographic parameters using for the first time multivariable logistic regression analysis with the inclusion of fetal Doppler. Shortcomings are the retrospective nature, the absence of long-term follow-up, and the impossibility to analyze stillbirth due to its low incidence.

Conclusion

In term healthy mothers with normal CTG perinatal outcome is influenced by low CPR, labor induction and low parity, while no effect is observed for fetal smallness, maternal age and length of interval examination-labor. These data do not support the consensus on universal induction at earlier weeks to prevent adverse outcome in case of advanced maternal age, advocating for a more individualized, customized, and less interventional conduction of the end of pregnancy based on fetal hemodynamics.

DISCLOSURES

Statement of Ethics.

IRB permission was obtained for the study (Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria La Fe, reference 2014/0063). Being a retrospective study there was no need to ask for informed consent.

Conflict of Interest Statement.

The authors report no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Figueras F, Gratacós E. Update on the diagnosis and classification of fetal growth restriction and proposal of a stage-based management protocol. *Fetal Diagn Ther.* 2014;36:86-98.
2. Lees CC, Stampalija T, Baschat A, da Silva Costa F, Ferrazzi E, Figueras F, Hecher K, Kingdom J, Poon LC, Salomon LJ, Unterscheider J. ISUOG Practice Guidelines: diagnosis and management of small-for-gestational-age fetus and fetal growth restriction. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2020;56:298-312.
3. Walker KF, George Bugg, Marion Macpherson, Carol McCormick, Chris Wildsmith, Gordon Smith, Jim Thornton. Induction of labour versus expectant management for nulliparous women over 35 years of age: a multi-centre prospective, randomised controlled trial. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2012;12:145.
4. Knight HE, Cromwell DA, Gurol-Urganci I, Harron K, Van der Meulen JH, Smith GCS. Perinatal mortality associated with induction of labour versus expectant management in nulliparous women aged 35 years or over: An English national cohort study. *PLoS Med* 2017;14:e1002425.
5. Morales-Roselló J, Khalil A, Morlando M, Papageorghiou A, Bhide A, Thilaganathan B. Changes in fetal Doppler indices as a marker of failure to reach growth potential at term. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2014;43:303-10
6. Morales-Roselló J, Khalil A, Morlando M, Hervás-Marín D, Perales-Marín A. Doppler reference values of the fetal vertebral and middle cerebral arteries, at 19-41 weeks gestation. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med.* 2015;28:338-43.
7. Acharya G, Wilsgaard T, Berntsen GK, et al. Reference ranges for serial measurements of umbilical artery Doppler indices in the second half of pregnancy. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2005;192:937-44.
8. Baschat AA, Gembruch U. The cerebroplacental Doppler ratio revisited. *Ultrasound*

Obstet Gynecol. 2003;21:124-127.

9. Figueras F, Meler E, Iraola A, Eixarch E, Coll O, Figueras J, Francis A, Gratacos E, Gardosi J. Customized birthweight standards for a Spanish population. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2008;136:20-4.

10. Ayres-de-Campos D, Spong CY, Chandrachan E; FIGO Intrapartum Fetal Monitoring Expert Consensus Panel. FIGO consensus guidelines on intrapartum fetal monitoring: Cardiotocography. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet.* 2015;131:13-24.

11. Chauhan SP, Rice MM, Grobman WA, Bailit J, Reddy UM, Wapner RJ, Varner MW, Thorp JM Jr, Leveno KJ, Caritis SN, Prasad M, Tita ATN, Saade G, Sorokin Y, Rouse DJ, Tolosa JE; MSCE, for the Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) Maternal-Fetal Medicine Units (MFMU) Network. Neonatal Morbidity of Small- and Large-for-Gestational-Age Neonates Born at Term in Uncomplicated Pregnancies. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2017;130:511-519.

12. Mendez-Figueroa H, Truong VT, Pedroza C, Khan AM, Chauhan SP. Small-for-gestational-age infants among uncomplicated pregnancies at term: a secondary analysis of 9 Maternal-Fetal Medicine Units Network studies. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2016;215:628.e1-628.e7.

13. Jacobsson B, Ladfors L, Milsom I. Advanced maternal age and adverse perinatal outcome. *Obstet Gynecol.* 2004;104:727-33.

14. Salem Yaniv S, Levy A, Wiznitzer A, Holcberg G, Mazor M, Sheiner E A significant linear association exists between advanced maternal age and adverse perinatal outcome. *Arch Gynecol Obstet.* 2011;283:755-9.

15. Bhattacharya S, Campbell DM, Liston WA, Bhattacharya S. Effect of Body Mass Index on pregnancy outcomes in nulliparous women delivering singleton babies. *BMC Public Health.* 2007;7:168.

16. The Athukorala C, Rumbold AR, Willson KJ, Crowther CA risk of adverse pregnancy

outcomes in women who are overweight or obese. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2010;10:56.

17. Kim SS, Zhu Y, Grantz KL, Hinkle SN, Chen Z, Wallace ME, Smarr MM, Epps NM, Mendola P. Obstetric and Neonatal Risks Among Obese Women Without Chronic Disease. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2016;128:104-12.

18. Marozio L, Picardo E, Filippini C, Mainolfi E, Berchiolla P, Cavallo F, Tancredi A, Benedetto C. Maternal age over 40 years and pregnancy outcome: a hospital-based survey. *J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2019;32:1602-1608.

19. Claramonte Nieto M, Meler Barrabes E, Garcia Martínez S, Gutiérrez Prat M, Serra Zantop B. Impact of aging on obstetric outcomes: defining advanced maternal age in Barcelona. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2019;19:342.

20. Carolan M. Maternal age ≥ 45 years and maternal and perinatal outcomes: a review of the evidence. *Midwifery*. 2013;29:479-89.

21. American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists. Antepartum fetal surveillance. Practice Bulletin 145, July 2014.

22. Morales-Roselló J, Cañada Martínez AJ, Scarinci E, Perales Marín A Comparison of Cerebroplacental Ratio, Intergrowth-21st Standards, Customized Growth, and Local Population References for the Prediction of Fetal Compromise: Which Is the Best Approach? . *Fetal Diagn Ther*. 2019;46:341-352.

23. Aliyu MH, Jolly PE, Ehiri JE, Salihu HM. High parity and adverse birth outcomes: exploring the maze. *Birth*. 2005;32:45-59.

24. Babinszki A, Kerenyi T, Torok O, Grazi V, Lapinski RH, Berkowitz RL. Perinatal outcome in grand and great-grand multiparity: effects of parity on obstetric risk factors. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 1999;181:669-74.

25. Kalogiannidis I, Margioulas-Siarkou C, Petousis S, Masoura S, Goutzioulis A, Traianos A, Prapas N, Agorastos T. Parity affects pregnancy outcomes in women 35 and older. *Clin*

Exp Obstet Gynecol 2011;38:146-9.

26. Kalayci H, Ozdemir H, Alkas D, Cok T, Tarim E. Is primiparity a risk factor for advanced maternal age pregnancies? J Matern Fetal Neonatal Med. 2017;30:1283-1287.

27. Garcia-Simon R, Figueras F, Savchev S, Fabre E, Gratacos E, Oros D perinatal outcome after labor induction for late-onset small-for-gestational-age fetuses. Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol. 2015;46:713-7.

28. Souter V, Painter I, Sitcov K, Caughey AB. Maternal and newborn outcomes with elective induction of labor at term. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2019;220:273.e1-273.e11.

29. Grobman WA, Caughey AB. Elective induction of labor at 39 weeks compared with expectant management: a meta-analysis of cohort studies. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2019;221:304-310.

30. Hersh AR, Skeith AE, Sargent JA, Caughey AB Induction of labor at 39 weeks of gestation versus expectant management for low-risk nulliparous women: a cost-effectiveness analysis. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2019;220:590.e1-590.e10.

31. Keulen JK, Bruinsma A, Kortekaas JC, van Dillen J, Bossuyt PM, Oudijk MA, Duijnhoven RG, van Kaam AH, Vandenbussche FP, van der Post JA, Mol BW, de Miranda E. Induction of labour at 41 weeks versus expectant management until 42 weeks (INDEX): multicentre, randomised non-inferiority trial. BMJ. 2019;364:l344.

32. Stock SJ, Ferguson E, Duffy A, Ford I, Chalmers J, Norman JE. Outcomes of elective induction of labour compared with expectant management: population based study. BMJ. 2012;344:e2838.

33. Gülmezoglu AM, Crowther CA, Middleton P, Heatley E Induction of labour for improving birth outcomes for women at or beyond term. Cochrane Database Syst Rev. 2012;6:CD004945.

34. Morales-Roselló J, Loscalzo G, Buongiorno S, Perales-Marín A. Cerebroplacental ratio and estimated fetal weight, the 2 different yardsticks. Am J Obstet Gynecol. 2019;221:664-

665.

LEGENDS

Figure 1.

Box and Whiskers graphs describing the values of BW centile, maternal age, CPR MoM, BMI, parity and induction of labor in fetuses with normal and adverse perinatal outcome. Only CPR MoM ($p < 0.01$), parity ($P < 0.05$) and induction of labor ($P < 0.01$), presented statistically significant differences.

Figure 2.

ROC curve representing the multivariable model for the prediction of APO, using clinical and sonographic parameters. Sensitivity=35% for a false positive rate (FPR) of 10% and 27% for a FPR of 5%, AUC=0.736, 95% CI= 0.655-0.818, $P < 0.0001$.

